

FRESH FRUITS AND VEGETABLES PRODUCTS EXPORT PERFORMANCE IN INDIA

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Abstract:

India is the second largest producer of fruits and vegetables in the world after China. Since 1991, the global export of fruits and vegetables has improved rapidly. The number of commodities as well as the number of varieties produced and traded have increased manifold during the past 30 years. There is an overall increase in the demand for fruits and vegetables for consumption in the fresh and processed form. Also there is a wide diversification in production pattern globally. In spite of being one of the largest producers of fruits and vegetables in the world, the export share of India is very low. The food processing industry in India is one of the largest in terms of production, consumption, export and growth prospects. However, only 2.2 percent of fruits and vegetables are processed in India against 83 percent in Malaysia, 30 percent in Thailand, 60-70 percent in United Kingdom and 70 percent Brazil. Therefore, the production of fruits and vegetables has been remarkable but its export share is very low / negligible and processing of fruits and vegetables is only 2.2 percent.

Key Words: Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products, export and data

Introduction:

Export is play a major role of development and growth of the countries. Exports are goods and services that are produced in one country and sold to buyers in another. Exports are incredibly important to modern economies because they offer people and firms many more markets for their goods. One of the core functions of diplomacy and foreign policy between governments is to foster economic trade, encouraging exports and imports for the benefit of all trading parties. India's diverse climate ensures availability of all varieties of fresh fruits & vegetables. It ranks second in fruits and vegetables production in the world, after China. As per National Horticulture Database (Second Advance Estimates) published by National Horticulture Board, during 2019-20, India produced 99.07 million metric tons of fruits and 191.77 million metric tons of vegetables. The area under cultivation of fruits stood at 6.66 million hectares while vegetables were cultivated at 10.35 million hectares. The vast production base offers India tremendous opportunities for export. During 2020-21, India exported fruits and vegetables worth Rs. 9,940.95 crores/ 1,342.14 USD Millions which comprised of fruits worth Rs. 4,971.22 crores/ 674.53 USD Millions and vegetables worth Rs. 4,969.73 crores/ 667.61 USD Millions. The major destinations for Indian fruits and vegetables are Bangladesh, UAE, Netherland, Nepal, Malaysia, UK, Sri Lanka, Oman and Qatar. Though India's share in the global market is still nearly 1% only, there is increasing acceptance of horticulture produce from the country. This has occurred due to concurrent developments in the areas of state-of-the-art cold chain infrastructure and quality assurance measures. Apart from large investment pumped in by the private sector, public sector has also taken initiatives and with APEDA's assistance several Centers for Perishable Cargoes and integrated post-harvest handling facilities have been set up in the country. Capacity building initiatives at the farmers, processors and exporters' levels has also contributed towards this effort.

Problem Statement:

- The potential for cultivating fruits and vegetables from domestic and export market is high.
- Despite the being the healthy demand for Indian fruits and vegetables abroad.
- The country faces the serious problems with finding exportable quality fruits and vegetables in sufficient amount.

Objectives:

- To study about the export performances of Fresh Fruits and vegetables products from India.
- To provide necessary suggestion based on the findings of the study.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the project is involved the export performance Fresh Fruits and Vegetables the export performance of Indian Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products is affected by the high demand. The study also gives growth rate and trend percentage of the export of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables goods year wise and also

country wise. The study provides suggestion to the Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products exporting industries to improve their performance.

Research Methodology:

Secondary Data:

Secondary data the secondary data is collected to supplement the primary data. The annual reports of sample units, publication of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products in the website of India Export Statistics-APEDA and industries, bulletins working and occasional papers of foreign trade preference analysis were used as important sources of secondary data for the study.

Limitations of the Study:

- The analysis made only by considering 12 Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products and 10 major countries.
- Time constraint is one of the limitations.

Review of Literature:

Kumar Govind., (2014) India is the second largest producer of fruits and vegetables in the world after China. Since 1991, the global export of fruits and vegetables has improved rapidly. The number of commodities as well as the number of varieties produced and traded have increased manifold during the past 30 years.

Muscogiuri et al., (2020).COVID-19 outbreak interrupted the daily routine and resulted in boredom which can be defined as high energy intake by the consumption of high amount of fat, carbohydrate, and proteins. In addition, quarantine caused stress in people and pushed them toward sugary foods for feeling positive, because carbohydrate-rich foods can be used as self-medicating components due to their ability to encourage serotonin production. However, these unhealthy eating habits may contribute to the development of obesity linked to the chronic inflammation and serious complications of COVID-19.

Bakalis et al., (2020); Cranfield, (2020)When the issue of how the COVID-19 pandemic affects consumers’ food demand is examined, it is seen that the demand varies depending on the price of foodstuffs, income level of consumers, socio demographic situation, consumption, and shopping preferences and time constraints. In addition, the number of visits to food store and spending money on food in per visit changed (Bakalis et al., 2020; Cranfield, 2020).

Exports of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables:

Table 1

Tema

Years	Fresh Onion 7031001	Growth Rate	Other Fresh Vegetables 7011000	Growth Rate	Walnuts - 8023100	Growth Rate	Fresh Mangoes - 8045020	Growth Rate	Fresh Grapes - 8061000	Growth Rate
2009-10	231943		481.31		287.46		20053.98		43106.53	
2010-11	177929	-23.288	1075.09	123	172.91	-40	16483.6	-18	39101.3	-9
2011-12	172300	-3.1635	601.97	-44	233.76	35	20974.3	27	51675.64	32
2012-13	196663	14.1398	331.7	-45	352.39	51	26471.78	26	98204.38	90
2013-14	316961	61.17	355.09	7	301.08	-15	28542.85	8	143707	46
2014-15	230054	-27.419	466.55	31	214.58	-29	30253.66	6	97276.92	-32
2015-16	309721	34.6295	467.12	0	429.45	100	32063.9	6	136225.6	40
2016-17	310606	0.28593	707.65	51	692.69	61	44366	38	178171.4	31
2017-18	308882	-0.5551	1331.93	88	794.03	15	38234.01	-14	189994.9	7
2018-19	346887	12.3041	656.81	-51	369.58	-53	40649.55	6	233525.1	23
2019-20	232070	-33.099	402.53	-39	110.7	-70	40021.35	-2	217686.8	-7
2020-21	282653	21.7968	685.67	70	440.26	298	27187.82	-32	229845.1	6
2021-22	297302	5.18252	381.84	-44	1271.77	189	29042.45	7	141888.6	-38
AAGR	5.16534			12		45		5		16
CAGR	-0.0205			-0.92		-0.12		57.77		-0.09

Interpretation:

The above table indicates that the Fresh Fruits and Vegetables product exporting from India. That varieties has contain many , and it classified for HS code basis , in this table the Fresh Onion, not carded combed (7031001) has calculated the financial years from 2009-10 to 2021-22. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 5 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Fresh onion, not carded combed (7031001) annual average growth rate is 5.16534. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.0205) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Other Fresh Vegetables (7011000) has calculated the financial years from 2009-10 to 2021-22. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 6 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Other Fresh Vegetables (7011000) annual average growth rate is 12. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.92) because of decrease in year by year. The Walnuts, carded or combed (8023100) has calculated the financial years from 2009-10 to 2021-22. This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 6 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Walnuts, carded or

combed (8023100) annual average growth rate is 45. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (0.12) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Fresh Mangoes (8045020) has calculated the financial years from 2009-10 to 2021-22. This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 4 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Fresh Mangoes (8045020) annual average growth rate is 5. The compound growth rate will defines the positive value (57.77) because of increase in year by year. The export of Fresh Grapes (8061000) has calculated the financial years from 2009- 10 to 2021-22. This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 5 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Fresh Grapes (8061000) annual average growth rate is 16. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.09) because of decrease in year by year.

Exports of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables:

Table 2

Years	Other Fresh Fruits 8030000	Growth Rate	Mango Pulp- 8045040	Growth Rate	Processed Vegetables- 7101000	Growth Rate	Others Grapes Dried 8062090	Growth Rate	Other Seed of Forage Plants 12092990	Growth Rate
2009-10	51354.8		74460.77		586.7		258.23		365.25	
2010-11	48610.4	-5	81893.27	10	3739.75	537	262.2	2	363.17	-1
2011-12	71631.1	47	62082.91	-24	3846.94	3	2519.85	861	707.06	95
2012-13	72688.1	1	60855.73	-2	1915.27	-50	854.59	-66	1150.15	63
2013-14	92436.9	27	77294.76	27	5406.56	182	628.52	-26	1419.87	23
2014-15	108406	17	84138.54	9	176.33	-97	607.8	-3	702.09	-51
2015-16	156729	45	79618.09	-5	575.33	226	1024.71	69	1370.33	95
2016-17	162964	4	84601.79	6	561.05	-2	1461.84	43	518.84	-62
2017-18	144376	-11	67392.14	-20	314.12	-44	722.44	-51	2678.38	416
2018-19	183457	27	65767.02	-2	639.37	104	599.83	-17	4307.74	61
2019-20	206582	13	58431.95	-11	597.57	-7	466.16	-22	4224.75	-2
2020-21	223331	8	71440.84	22	3956.68	562	369.38	-21	4691.86	11
2021-22	256909	15	86078.23	20	6248.31	58	734.41	99	2613.44	-44
AAGR		16		2		123		72		50
CAGR		-0.13		3.93		-0.18		-0.08		-0.15

Interpretation:

The above table indicates that the Fresh Fruits and Vegetables product exporting from India. That varieties has contain many, and it classified for HS code basis, in this table the Other Fresh Fruits, not carded combed (8030000) has calculated the financial years from 2009-10 to 202122. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 2 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Other Fresh Fruits, not carded combed (8030000) annual average growth rate is 16. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.13) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Mango Pulp (8045040) has calculated the financial years from 2009-10 to 2021-22. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 6 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Mango Pulp (8045040) annual average growth rate is 2. The compound growth rate will defines the positive value (3.93) because of increase in year by year. The Processed Vegetables (7101000) has calculated the financial years from 2009-10 to 202122. This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 5 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Processed Vegetables (7101000) annual average growth rate is 123. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.18) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Others Grapes Dried (8062090) has calculated the financial years from 2009-10 to 2021-22. This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 7 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Others Grapes Dried (80620900) annual average growth rate is 72. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.08) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Other Seed of Forage Plants (12092990) has calculated the financial years from 2009- 10 to 2021-22. This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 5 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Other Seed of Forage Plants (12092990) annual average growth rate is 50. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.15) because of decrease in year by year.

Findings:

1. The Fresh onion (7031001), The AAGR is 5.16534. The CAGR will defines the negative value (-0.0205) because of decrease in year by year.
2. The other fresh vegetables (7011000), The AAGR is12. The CAGR will defines the negative value (-0.92) because of decrease in year by year.
3. The Walnuts (8023100), The AAGR is 45. The CAGR will defines the negative value (-0.12) because of decrease in year by year.
4. The Fresh Mangoes (8045020), The AAGR is 5.TheCAGRwill defines the positive value (57.77) because of increase in year by year.
5. The Fresh Grapes (8061000), The AAGR is16. The CAGR will defines the negative value (-0.09) because of decrease in year by year.

6. The Other Fresh Fruits (8030000), The AAGR is 16. The CAGR will defines the negative value (-0.13) because of decrease in year by year.
7. The Mango Pulp (8045040) the AAGR is 2. The CAGR will defines the positive value (3.93) because of increase in year by year.
8. The Processed Vegetables (7101000), The AAGR is 123. The CAGR will defines the negative value (-0.18) because of decrease in year by year.
9. The Others Grapes Dried (8062090). The AAGR is 72. The CAGR will defines the negative value (-0.08) because of decrease in year by year.
10. The Other Seed of Forage Plants (12092990), The AAGR is 50. The CAGR will defines the negative value (-0.15) because of decrease in year by year.

Suggestions:

- This post explains export process of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables exports and the government rules to export Fresh fruits and Vegetables products, different precautions to be taken care to export them, export documentation to export Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products.
- This tables are been indicate a Fresh Fruits and Vegetables product markets in internationally, to be make a some special schemes the Government of India will focus this Fresh Fruits and Vegetables export.
- The government and exports are mainly focus on this product, when this product is a major raw material of Fruits and Vegetables.
- The government to provide extra some subsidies and incentives for this exporters. The Fresh Fruits and Vegetables product has most demanded product in foreign market.

Conclusion:

In this case the Fresh Fruits and Vegetables product export will studied. To know about the India's Fresh Fruits and Vegetables production states and study about the exporting data. This study will using the methodology of secondary data, that data are collected in India Export Statistics (APEDA) web page. To using some statics formulas of growth rate, annual average growth rate, compound annual growth rate. And some literature reviews are collected when to know about the trends and this products value range. This study has to been know about the Fresh Fruits and Vegetables product's various verities are exporting values, it will be make details of products foreign demands. When the exporting is a more profitable business comparing to the domestics business. In this case to find out the major analysis of growth rate, annual average growth rate and compound average growth rate. This case to using the thirteen years of export data will used that data are making a positive and negative results will there. Most of products will make a many negative growth rates, it will be makes a future analysis of decrease the growth but the demand will be a standard. So, these of above things are studied in this component.

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